

CYTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MONOCYTES IN COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN WITH PROTEIN-ENERGY MALNUTRITION

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Abstract. *Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is one of the leading causes of childhood mortality worldwide. Every year, more than 700,000 children under 5 years of age die from pneumonia (about 14% of all deaths in this age group) [1]. The vast majority of these deaths can be prevented through timely diagnosis and treatment. Children in the first three years of life are especially vulnerable to pneumonia: the anatomical features of the respiratory tract and the immaturity of the immune system make them susceptible to the rapid spread of infection [2]. Risk factors for severe CAP include prematurity, congenital malformations, weakened immunity, and malnutrition. In particular, protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) is widespread in developing countries and, according to WHO estimates, malnutrition occurs in 20-30% of young children. Malnutrition weakens the immune response and slows recovery: in PEM, cellular immunity is impaired, the thymus gland atrophies, and susceptibility to infections, including respiratory infections, increases [3,4]. A systemic review has shown that in malnourished children, the activity of acid phosphatase in leukocytes is often elevated, indicating compensatory activation of the phagocytic system [5,6,7]. Given the importance of the macrophage link in protecting the lungs, cytochemical examination of peripheral blood monocytes can serve as a marker of immune reactivity in CAP. Cytochemistry allows one to determine the intracellular activity of enzymes and, unlike conventional biochemistry, evaluates this indicator at the level of entire cell populations. In particular, the activity of monocyte myeloperoxidase (MP), acid phosphatase (AP), and succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) reflects the degree of the immune response and metabolic disorders. However, the roles of these indicators in CAP and PEM in children have not been studied.*

Keywords: *community-acquired pneumonia, protein-energy malnutrition, cytochemistry.*

Introduction. In the childhood age group, community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide [8]. Approximately 120 million cases of pneumonia in children and up to 1.3 million deaths are registered annually; about 80% of these deaths occur in children under 2 years of age in developing countries [9]. There are two age peaks in pneumonia incidence: the first, most pronounced, occurs in early childhood and preschool age (2-3 years), which is associated with the immaturity of the respiratory system and immunity of infants [10]. Infants and young children are especially vulnerable to CAP due to their anatomical and physiological characteristics (narrow bronchial lumen, low mucociliary function) and immaturity of cellular immunity [8,10].

Monocytes are an important part of innate immunity and participate in the anti-infective response (phagocytosis, antigen presentation, cytokine production). Cytochemical methods allow us to evaluate the intracellular activity of monocyte enzymes, which reflects their metabolic status and degree of activation. Thus, the activity of succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) correlates with the

energy potential of the cell, the activity of acid phosphatase (AP) with lysosomal function, and the activity of myeloperoxidase (MP) with the phagocytic activity of monocytes [11,12]. Changes in these enzymatic indicators can reveal the severity of infection and the degree of metabolic overload of immune cells.

Protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) in children is a global health problem, especially in resource-poor regions. According to WHO, malnutrition is an indirect cause of up to 45% of deaths in children under 5 years of age, as it significantly weakens the body's immune response [13]. With PEM, the barrier functions of the mucous membranes are disrupted, the concentration of complement components decreases, and the thymus atrophies, which makes children more susceptible to infections [12]. Modern studies show that children with PEM have a more severe course of pneumonia - prolonged fever is observed, the incidence of complications is high, and longer treatment is required [14,15]. These data emphasize the need to study the cytochemical parameters of monocytes to assess the severity of inflammation and prognosis in children with CAP against the background of PEM.

The aim of the study: to identify the cytochemical features of the metabolic activity of peripheral monocytes in young children with community-acquired pneumonia against the background of protein-energy malnutrition, as well as to assess their clinical significance for the prognosis of the disease and optimization of therapy.

Materials and methods. The study included 58 children aged 6 months to 3 years diagnosed with CAP with PEM. Based on clinical data, the following groups were identified: children with CAP with PEM (n=36) and children with CAP without pronounced PEM (n=22) with complicated course (cardiorespiratory and toxic manifestations). The comparison group included 20 practically healthy children of the same age. The diagnosis of CAP was established based on clinical (cough, difficulty breathing, fever), laboratory and radiological criteria. The degree of PEM (I-III) was determined by weight deficit and clinical signs. All children underwent general clinical examination, questionnaires and anthropometry.

Mononuclear cells were isolated from peripheral blood and stained for enzyme activity using standard methods: MP was determined using the Quaglini method et al., AP, according to Gololberg-Barka (Gololberg and Barka) and SDH by the quantitative method of Nartsissov. The result was the cytochemical index (CI) – the percentage of positive cells or the intensity of staining in arbitrary units. The determinations were made at the following stages: upon admission (onset of the disease), in the acute phase and in the recovery period (clinical improvement). Statistical processing included the calculation of average values and comparison with the control group (Mann-Whitney U test, $p < 0.05$ was considered significant).

Results. The examined children with CAP and PEM had a severe course of the disease. Fever persisting for more than 6 days with signs of intoxication was noted in 32% of patients; protracted broncho-obstructive syndrome (wheezing for more than 12 days) was noted in 18.4%. Damage to the lung tissue with signs of destruction developed by the 2nd-3rd day of the disease in 11.3% of patients. Almost all children (88%) had PEM stage II (normal weight 70-80% of the expected), which was accompanied by pronounced depletion of subcutaneous fat (fat rolls on the abdomen and chest disappeared) and hypotension of the abdominal muscles. The skin of 78.5% of children was pale, 57% had dry skin, 36% had a tendency to form venous "nets" when bending their arms. Hypovitaminosis was detected in 80% of cases: 54.7% had cracks in the corners of the mouth, 11% had skin marbling, 9.3% had peeling and hyperpigmentation of the skin. 78.2% of children had decreased skin turgor and muscle tone. 76% of patients had decreased appetite; 11.3%

developed food intolerance. Children were psychoemotionally exhausted: 57% were restless, irritable, 18.7% were anxious, 14.3% were tearful or lethargic. Thermoregulatory disorders were also found: 93.1% had widely fluctuating temperatures (sometimes more than 1° C per day). Complications (draining pleurisy, grade II-III respiratory failure) were found in 18 children. Table 1 summarizes the most common clinical and anthropometric signs of PEM in children with CAP from our cohort.

Table 1. Clinical and anthropometric features in children with CAP and PEM (study results).

Clinical signs and symptoms	% of children (n=58)
II degree of PEM (weight deficit 20–30%)	88
Paleness of the skin and mucous membranes	78.5
Dry, flabby skin	57
Labile temperature regime (>1 °C)	93.1
Decreased appetite	76
Lethargy, irritability	57
Digestive disorders (diarrhea, vomiting)	11.3

Cytochemical analysis of monocytes revealed a pronounced dysfunction of their activity. In the acute phase of the disease, the activity of SDH was significantly reduced compared to healthy children ($p < 0.001$), whereas in the recovery period it increased sharply and exceeded the norm (control). The activity of acid phosphatase was maximum in the acute phase ($p < 0.001$) with a gradual decrease towards recovery (but remained above the norm).

The MP level showed the least variability: in most patients, the MP concentration in monocytes was increased (as a sign of activation of oxidative mechanisms of phagocytosis). This was especially evident in the purulent-destructive form of CAP: in such children, MP activity increased already in the early stages and by the end of the treatment period reached $\approx 150\%$ of the norm ($p < 0.001$).

Similarly, the activity of AP in children with lung destruction was highest in the acute phase. In patients with severe course and pronounced acidosis, a sharper suppression of SDH was observed at the onset of the disease and a more rapid restoration of its level in dynamics.

Figure 1 schematically shows the typical dynamics of cytochemical indices of monocytes (relative to control values) in children with CAP against the background of PEM: the greatest decrease in SDH in the acute phase and an increase in AP, a moderate increase in MP by the recovery period. These changes reflect the transition from acute stress metabolism (activation of lysosomes and inflammation) to the restorative mode of cells.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the activity of monocyte enzymes (MP – myeloperoxidase, AP – acid phosphatase, SDH – succinate dehydrogenase) in children with CAP and PEM.

Discussion. The obtained data confirm that EP against the background of PEM is more severe than with normal nutrition. Protein-energy deficiency contributes to the suppression of the cellular link of immunity: with kwashiorkor and marasmus, the formation of T-cells and macrophages is disrupted, which increases the risk of pneumonia and other bacterial infections. Our clinical observations are consistent with this - in children with PEM, CAP was accompanied by persistent intoxication and a protracted course. It is known that malnourished children have weakened nonspecific resistance and a tendency to immunoglobulin deficiency and phagocytosis.

Cytochemical changes in monocytes confirm metabolic disturbances in CAP+PEM. A decrease in the activity of the mitochondrial enzyme SDH in the acute phase indicates suppression of aerobic metabolism (probably due to metabolic acidosis and hypoxia), while an increase in the activity of lysosomal AP reflects increased phagocytic activity of macrophage system cells. Similar phenomena have been previously described in malnourished children: for example, in children with malnutrition, an increase in the activity of acid phosphatase in leukocytes is noted. In purulent complications of CAP, activation of monocytic mechanisms is especially noticeable – an increase in MP and AP, which is consistent with data on an increase in the oxidative response of phagocytes under severe infection. In total, these changes indicate an overload of the immune system and compensatory mobilization of enzymatic reserves in response to the pathogenic load.

Conclusions. Community-acquired pneumonia in young children with protein-energy malnutrition is characterized by a severe protracted course and a high risk of complications. Malnutrition weakens cellular immunity, which is confirmed by changes in cytochemical markers of monocytes (decreased SDH, increased AP and MP in the acute phase). Cytochemical analysis of peripheral monocytes can serve as an additional indicator of the severity of infection and the effectiveness of treatment: monitoring the activity of SDH, AP and MP allow to assess the dynamics of the immune response at the cellular level. The obtained results substantiate the need for a systemic approach to the treatment of such children, including not only antibacterial therapy, but also correction of nutritional status. Further research should be aimed at developing targeted methods for the treatment of pneumonia in malnourished children, as well as identifying prognostic cytochemical markers of the severity of the disease.

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